

Volumetric properties and ultrasonic velocities of binary mixtures of 2-butanone with alkyl acetates at (298.15 to 308.15) K

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Abstract : Densities and ultrasonic velocity of the binary mixtures of 2-butanone with alkyl acetates such as methyl acetate, ethyl acetate, 1-propyl acetate and 1-butyl acetate were measured at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K over the entire composition range. This experimental data were used to calculate excess molar volumes (V^E), deviations in isentropic compressibility ($\Delta\kappa_s$). These results were fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial equation and results have been discussed in terms of molecular interaction and structural effects. The excess properties were found to be either positive or negative depending on the molecular interaction and the nature of liquid mixtures.

Keywords : Binary mixtures, alkyl acetates, 2-butanone.

Introduction

In the technological, biological and industrial applications binary mixtures are frequently used as they provide a wide choice of solvents with appropriate compositions and properties, such solvents also influence the rate of a reaction differently from those of pure solvents. Therefore the study of intermolecular interactions in the binary liquid mixtures is of considerable importance. Although this field has been widely exploited, the basic processes are still relatively poorly understood at a detailed molecular level¹. Thermodynamic properties such as densities and ultrasonic velocities of pure liquids and of their binary liquid mixtures over the whole composition range measured at several temperatures are useful for a full understanding of their thermodynamic and transport properties as well as practical chemical engineering purposes². The studies of excess functions of binary liquid mixtures are useful in understanding the nature and strength of molecular interactions between the component molecules³. 2-Butanone is an interesting solvent widely employed in scientific studies and industrial applications, especially for the solvating properties associated with its own character as an aprotic and protophilic medium⁴, a high dipole moment ($\mu_1 = 2.75$ D), and relatively low static dielectric constant ($\epsilon = 18.51$) at 20 °C. Esters are used

as plasticizing agents during polymer processing to impart favorable thermo elastic properties⁵. In the present paper we report density (ρ) and ultrasonic velocity (u) for the binary mixtures of 2-butanone with alkyl acetate at different temperatures. The calculated excess quantities from such data have been interpreted in terms of molecular interactions and structural effects.

Results and discussion

The comparison of physical properties of various pure liquids along with their literature values at 298.15 K are recorded in Table 1. The density, ultrasonic velocity, and their excess properties as excess molar volumes, isentropic compressibility for binary mixtures are presented in Tables 2 to 4.

Table 1. Comparison of experimental densities and ultrasonic velocities of pure liquids with literature values at 298.15 K

Pure liquids	ρ (g cm ⁻³)		u (ms ⁻¹)	
	Expt	Lit	Expt	Lit
2-Butanone	0.79970	0.7997 ¹⁰	1209.0	-
Methyl acetate	0.92673	0.92698 ¹²	1163.0	1161.0 ⁵
Ethyl acetate	0.89384	0.89430 ¹³	1145.0	1144.0 ⁵
1-Propyl acetate	0.88313	0.88310 ¹⁴	1172.0	1172.0 ¹⁴
1-Butyl acetate	0.87637	0.87530 ⁵	1195.0	1190.0 ¹⁴

Table-3 (contd.)

0.8698	0.80813	1152.4	0.1475	42.2396
0.9350	0.80128	1166.9	0.0888	23.0091
1.0000	0.79481	1184.0	0.0000	0.0006
2-Butanone + ethyl acetate				
0.0000	0.88757	1123.0	0.0000	0.0004
0.0803	0.87981	1119.1	0.1017	13.8426
0.1582	0.87241	1114.9	0.1751	28.1287
0.2340	0.86522	1111.7	0.2367	40.8410
0.3076	0.85826	1109.4	0.2838	52.0350
0.3792	0.85152	1108.3	0.3174	61.1286
0.4489	0.84492	1108.3	0.3460	68.3103
0.5167	0.83861	1013.8	0.3525	73.0080
0.5827	0.83252	1109.6	0.3445	74.7416
0.6470	0.82658	1112.5	0.3295	73.4178
0.7096	0.82082	1117.1	0.3041	69.3880
0.7706	0.81528	1131.3	0.2633	61.8264
0.8301	0.80992	1140.8	0.2114	51.9236
0.8882	0.80464	1152.7	0.1597	38.2951
0.9448	0.79961	1166.7	0.0886	21.4930
1.0000	0.79481	1184.0	0.0000	0.0006
2-Butanone + 1-propyl acetate				
0.0000	0.87726	1128.7	0.0000	0.0006
0.0919	0.87018	1125.1	0.1383	12.8126
0.1789	0.86351	1121.7	0.2307	25.1427
0.2615	0.85696	1118.7	0.3161	36.9338
0.3399	0.85069	1116.9	0.3742	46.6227
0.4146	0.84466	1116.1	0.4107	54.5078
0.4857	0.83885	1116.6	0.4286	60.0402
0.5534	0.83323	1118.2	0.4321	63.5521
0.6181	0.82783	1121.4	0.4177	64.1314
0.6799	0.82261	1126.1	0.3906	62.0063
0.7391	0.81759	1132.1	0.3486	57.5348
0.7957	0.81272	1139.3	0.2979	51.0033
0.8500	0.80805	1148.5	0.2325	41.1206
0.9020	0.80344	1158.5	0.1690	30.1427
0.9520	0.79912	1169.7	0.0807	17.2501
1.0000	0.79481	1184.0	0.0000	0.0006
2-Butanone + 1-butyl acetate				
0.0000	0.87129	1175.0	0.0000	0.0002
0.1032	0.86442	1165.4	0.1963	13.6385
0.1986	0.85802	1157.7	0.3250	25.1292
0.2871	0.85189	1151.8	0.4191	34.5250
0.3694	0.84606	1147.5	0.4770	41.8648
0.4461	0.84049	1144.9	0.5063	46.8436
0.5178	0.83513	1143.6	0.5152	50.0013
0.5850	0.83001	1143.6	0.5011	51.2039

Table-3 (contd.)

0.6480	0.82509	1145.1	0.4700	50.0988
0.7073	0.82034	1147.6	0.4267	47.4813
0.7631	0.81577	1151.6	0.3703	42.5154
0.8158	0.81128	1156.1	0.3135	36.9212
0.8657	0.80692	1160.9	0.2501	30.9550
0.9128	0.80281	1167.1	0.1661	22.7468
0.9575	0.79867	1175.1	0.0948	12.0538
1.0000	0.79481	1184.0	0.0000	0.0006

Table 4. Values of density, ultrasonic velocity and excess properties of binary liquid mixtures of 2-butanone with alkyl acetates at 308.15 K

x_1	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	u (ms ⁻¹)	v^E (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta\kappa_s$ (T Pa ⁻¹)
2-Butanone + methyl acetate				
0.0000	0.91623	1119.6	0.0000	0.0000
0.0684	0.90578	1109.7	0.0697	21.0703
0.1365	0.89581	1101.4	0.1166	40.0195
0.2044	0.88591	1095.7	0.1772	55.2838
0.2720	0.87644	1091.5	0.2171	68.0623
0.3394	0.86724	1088.2	0.2500	79.4096
0.4065	0.85827	1087.2	0.2790	86.7228
0.4734	0.84962	1087.7	0.2940	91.1857
0.5401	0.84123	1089.5	0.3000	93.1497
0.6065	0.83308	1093.6	0.2980	90.7546
0.6727	0.82525	1099.7	0.2785	84.4609
0.7386	0.81764	1106.7	0.2510	76.4429
0.8043	0.81026	1116.3	0.2136	63.7066
0.8698	0.80316	1128.1	0.1596	47.1105
0.9350	0.79641	1143.4	0.0801	24.6323
1.0000	0.78978	1160.4	0.0000	0.0001
2-Butanone + ethyl acetate				
0.0000	0.88123	1098.0	0.0000	0.0003
0.0803	0.87333	1094.3	0.1307	15.0225
0.1582	0.86599	1089.6	0.2097	31.5363
0.2340	0.85878	1086.1	0.2856	46.1040
0.3076	0.85178	1083.8	0.3490	58.5132
0.3792	0.84508	1082.9	0.3891	68.1789
0.4489	0.83864	1083.3	0.4103	75.2414
0.5167	0.83241	1084.8	0.4179	80.0798
0.5827	0.82643	1088.1	0.4071	81.3003
0.6470	0.82066	1092.7	0.3822	79.8984
0.7096	0.81507	1099.1	0.3463	75.0238
0.7706	0.80961	1107.2	0.3051	67.0241
0.8301	0.80443	1116.9	0.2410	56.0301
0.8882	0.79936	1129.1	0.1733	40.8500

Table-4 (contd.)

0.9448	0.79438	1143.4	0.1042	22.5099
1.0000	0.78978	1160.4	0.0000	0.0000
2-Butanone + 1-propyl acetate				
0.0000	0.87139	1104.0	0.0000	0.0008
0.0919	0.86429	1100.4	0.1512	14.0706
0.1789	0.85738	1096.1	0.2846	29.4514
0.3399	0.85087	1093.2	0.3733	42.1778
0.4146	0.84459	1091.1	0.4405	53.4043
0.4857	0.83855	1090.5	0.4856	61.7628
0.5534	0.83227	1090.8	0.5066	68.2555
0.6181	0.82724	1093.1	0.5052	70.8149
0.6799	0.82191	1096.6	0.4882	70.9661
0.7391	0.81678	1101.3	0.4558	68.7257
0.7957	0.81188	1107.8	0.4046	63.0088
0.7270	0.80714	1115.8	0.3434	54.5483
0.8500	0.80259	1125.4	0.2687	43.2560
0.9020	0.79816	1135.8	0.1889	30.7476
0.9520	0.79391	1147.1	0.0970	16.8664
1.0000	0.78978	1160.4	0.0000	0.0000
2-Butanone + 1-butyl acetate				
0.0000	0.86623	1165.6	0.0000	0.0001
0.1032	0.85915	1153.6	0.2303	15.5670
0.1986	0.85262	1143.8	0.3789	28.7855
0.2871	0.86438	1136.1	0.4891	39.6587
0.3694	0.84048	1130.9	0.5563	47.1235
0.4461	0.83485	1127.1	0.5928	52.7702
0.5178	0.82951	1124.7	0.5978	56.3966
0.5850	0.82439	1124.1	0.5823	57.2535
0.6480	0.81949	1124.9	0.5471	55.9082
0.7073	0.81485	1126.7	0.4882	52.9315
0.7631	0.81032	1129.5	0.4254	48.4613
0.8158	0.80589	1134.2	0.3600	40.9583
0.8657	0.80174	1138.5	0.2701	34.1263
0.9128	0.79769	1144.5	0.1780	24.6235
0.9575	0.79362	1151.3	0.0979	14.1492
1.0000	0.78978	1160.4	0.0000	0.0000

The excess molar volumes of binary mixtures were calculated by using equation,

$$V^E = ((x_1M_1 + x_2M_2)/\rho) - (x_1V_1 + x_2V_2) \quad (1)$$

where, x_1 , x_2 , M_1 , M_2 , V_1 and V_2 are mole fractions, molecular weights and molar volumes of first and second components respectively.

The ultrasonic velocity (u) is obtained by using the

knowledge of wavelength (λ) and frequency (f),

$$u = \lambda \times f \quad (2)$$

The measured values of ultrasonic velocities are used to calculate isentropic compressibility using equation as given below :

$$\kappa_s = 1/u^2\rho \quad (3)$$

The deviation of isentropic compressibility of binary mixtures were calculated by using equation,

$$\Delta\kappa_s = \kappa_s - x_1\kappa_{s1} - x_2\kappa_{s2} \quad (4)$$

where κ_s is the isentropic compressibility of the mixture, κ_{s1} , κ_{s2} , x_1 and x_2 is the isentropic compressibility of pure components 1 and 2, mole fraction of components 1 and 2 respectively. The calculated excess molar volumes (V^E) and deviation in isentropic compressibility ($\Delta\kappa_s$) and reported in Table 2, were correlated by Redlich-Kister polynomial⁶, by using the relation,

$$\Delta Y = x_1x_2\sum_{a_i}(x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (5)$$

The coefficients in eq. (5) were estimated by the least square fit method and the standard deviations were calculated by using the relation,

$$\sigma = [\sum (\Delta Y_{\text{Expt.}} - \Delta Y_{\text{Calcd.}})^2 / (D - N)]^{0.5} \quad (6)$$

where D and N are the number of data points and parameters, respectively.

Regression results for excess molar volumes and deviation in isentropic compressibility, of binary mixtures of 2-butanone with alkyl acetate such as methyl acetate, ethyl acetate, 1-propyl acetate, and 1-butyl acetate at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 K temperatures are reported in Table 5. The graphical variation of excess molar volume (V^E) for the binary mixtures of 2-butanone with four alkyl acetates with increasing mole fractions of 2-butanone at 298.15 K is shown in Fig. 1. The values of excess molar volumes are found to be positive for all the systems. It is established that sign and magnitude of (V^E) gives a good estimate of the unlike interactions in the binary mixtures. Generally, (V^E) can be considered arising from three types of interaction between component molecules :

Physical interaction mainly consisting of dispersion forces or weak dipole-dipole interaction and making a positive contribution^{2,3}.

Chemical or specific interactions which includes charge transfer, formation of hydrogen bonds and other complex

Table 5. Coefficients of Redlich-Kisters equation and the corresponding standard deviations (σ) for the binary mixtures at 298.15 K

System	a_0	a_1	a_2	σ
	V^E ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)			
2-Butanone + methyl acetate	1579.69	1489.19	-3646.28	525.01
2-Butanone + ethyl acetate	1.033	0.2655	0.1105	0.0683
2-Butanone + 1-propyl acetate	1.389	0.2515	8.766	0.0026
2-Butanone + 1-butyl acetate	1.1439	0.1021	0.0567	0.0028
	$\Delta\kappa_s$ (T Pa^{-1})			
2-Butanone + methyl acetate	295.0306	-1.8928	25.8628	0.2601
2-Butanone + ethyl acetate	247.1760	103.5766	10.1119	0.2162
2-Butanone + 1-propyl acetate	177.3630	124.3240	90.1743	1199.81
2-Butanone + 1-butyl acetate	163.9579	61.5971	14.5335	0.4256

Fig. 2. Variation of deviations in isentropic compressibility $\Delta\kappa_s$ against mole fraction x_1 of 2-butanone at 303.15 K : (◆) methyl acetate, (○) ethyl acetate, (▲) propyl acetate, (Δ) butyl acetate.

forming interactions resulting in negative contribution.

The structural contributions arising from geometrical fitting of one component into other due to difference in molar volumes resulting in negative (V^E). The systems where dispersion, induction and dipolar forces are operating, the values of excess molar volume are found to be positive, whereas the existence of specific interactions between the mixing components of the various binary systems tends to make excess molar volume negative⁷. The positive V^E values at equimolar concentration follow the order : 1-butyl acetate > 1-propyl acetate > ethyl acetate > methyl acetate.

Fig. 2 shows the graphical variation of deviation in isentropic compressibility ($\Delta\kappa_s$) for the binary mixtures of 2-butanone with four alkyl acetates with increasing mole fractions of 2-butanone at 298.15 K. In Fig. 2, the

values of isentropic compressibility are found to be positive for all the systems. The negative values of $\Delta\kappa_s$ for the systems represent strong specific interactions whereas the positive values represent the weak interactions or dominance of dispersion forces^{8,9}. The similar trend is observed in V^E and $\Delta\kappa_s$. The order of decrease in $\Delta\kappa_s$ values with respect to increase in CH_2 group is methyl acetate > ethyl acetate > 1-propyl acetate > 1-butyl acetate.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, one can say that dispersion type interaction is observed in case of all these binary mixtures of 2-butanone with alkyl acetate which makes the effect of dispersion forces more dominating, it has been reported that since normally dispersive interaction between unlike molecules is weaker than those between like molecules.

Experimental

All the organic liquids used in the present study were of analytical reagent grade and were obtained from S.D. Fine Chemicals. They were further purified according to the procedure described in literature^{10,11}. The binary liquid mixtures were prepared by mixing known masses of pure liquids in airtight-stoppered bottles in order to minimize the evaporation losses. All measurements of mass were performed on a Mettler one pan balance (E-Mettler, Zurich), which can read up to fifth place of decimal, with an accuracy of ± 0.05 mg.

The densities of the pure liquids and their binary mixtures were measured using the single arm capillary pycnometer having bulk volume of approximately 5 cm^3 and a capillary bore with an internal diameter of 0.75 mm. The accuracy in the density measurements was found to be of $\pm 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

The ultrasonic velocities were measured at 1 MHz with a single crystal variable path interferometer (F-81 Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) and the accuracy of ultrasonic measurement was $\pm 0.1\%$. For all the measurements, the temperature was controlled by circulating the water through an ultra thermostat JULABO F-25 (made in Germany) which has an accuracy of ± 0.02 °C.

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